

Recommendations for Responsible Microbiome Research and Innovation

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Executive summary

This deliverable builds on our previous deliverable (D7.1) submitted a year ago (in April 2023) and focussed on ethical and governance issues in microbiome research.

In the *Introduction* we explain how microbiome research reflects and contributes to our changing worldview, emphasising connectedness and embeddedness in the web of life, seeing life as processes of sympoiesis (= making a living world together). This means that the science of life must be sympoietic (i.e. collaborative and interdisciplinary) as well, to broaden our perspective by taking cultural, behavioural and socio-economic aspects into account.

In *Chapter 1* this is elaborated along three conceptual pathways. Besides the concept of sympoiesis (introduced by Donna Haraway), we argue that philosophical reflections on microbiome research can be developed along three lines, building on the work of Michel Foucault, connecting new practices of knowledge (e.g., next generation microbiome sequencing) with new practices of power (informed public health policies devoted to fostering population health) and new practices of the self (which include microbiome awareness and stewardship). Finally, we consider how microbiome research resonates with Gilbert Simondon's notion of individuation as an ecological and relational rather than egocentric understanding of the self.

Chapter 2 contains the results of an empirical turn in our research by presenting and analysing the outcomes of expert interviews focussing on three sets of questions: how should we see our relationship with our microbiome? How would you define microbiome health? And what constitutes responsible microbiome research? We conclude that microbiome research should not focus primarily on marketable products but should first and foremost foster public understanding of the microbiome as diverse, interactive, dynamic, relational, and continuously changing. Responsible microbiome research should take the global social context into account, for instance by not only focussing on issues that are mostly relevant to affluent consumers in the USA and Europe, but also study the impact of the global market of unhealthy food products on local food habits in less affluent regions. Deliberations about the microbiome should take the broader social and cultural dimension into account. For instance, if we assess the pros and cons of marketed microbiome product, we should not only consider the physiological consequences, but also the impact on food habits, family culture and social practices, as well as the inherent uncertainty of scientific knowledge.

Chapter 3 presents the results of the online public survey we conducted in four countries (France, Germany, South Korea and Taiwan). We found willingness to monitor the health of one's microbiome (especially, in the European countries) and to adjust one's lifestyle to improve it (across all 4 countries). Baseline public perceptions of microbes were slightly negative to neutral. Following a brief reflection on the role of microbiome in our body, the respondents reported a positive change in their perceptions towards microbes and the microbial world.

In *Chapter 4* we address a specific aspect of "sympoietic" research, namely consortium authorship. Although consortium authorship has important benefits, e.g. acknowledging the importance of collaboration, it also raises a number of questions. We conclude that consortium authorship is part of sympoietic practices of knowledge and that authorship ambiguities in terms of contribution and accountability can be addressed by combining it with individual authorship.

In the concluding *Chapter 5* we indicate how philosophical reflection can contribute to microbiome research (for instance by contributing to our reflections on the concept of microbiome health) while we see opportunities for broadening our knowledge base, making research even more relational, collaborative, participatory, sympoietic and responsible by including public and societal knowledge in our research methodologies (epistemic inclusion).

Introduction: responsible microbiome research

From pathogens to web of life: a dialectical view

It has been estimated that the human microbiome consists of up to 100 trillion cells, tenfold the number of human cells, while the total number of protein-coding genes in the human genome is only a small percentage of the genes actually found in our metagenome (Qin et al 2010). The human body, especially our central lumen, the gut, is pervaded by microorganisms. This awareness affects the way we see ourselves.¹ Initially, e.g. in traditional and indigenous worldviews, human beings tend to adopt a holistic perspective, seeing themselves as part of nature (the first moment, dialectically speaking).

Subsequently, during modernism, humans began to see themselves as separate from nature, so that the initial sense of unity was *negated*. Microbes were conceived in terms of otherness, as something threatening, external and foreign. In the 1880s for instance, during the era of Pasteur and Koch, microbes were primarily conceived as pathogens. With the help of microscopes, microbes were objectified, they became an “object”, or *Gegenstand* in German, which is quite close to being an opponent (*Gegner*). Science allowed us to immunise ourselves against this threat, via hygiene and vaccination, keeping dangerous microbes at bay, distancing ourselves from them. Although microscopes as research contrivances bring the microbial world closer to us, allowing us to zoom in on microscopic entities, they create an ontological distance between *subject* and *object*. The microbe becomes primarily a pathogen, an opponent, a threat. Vaccination campaigns and public health policies assert and increase this ontological distance.

The philosopher Friedrich Nietzsche echoed this when he argued that pathogens also exist in culture, and that civilisations are exposed to cultural pandemics (e.g., the conversion to Christianity as an ideological epidemiological event, with Christian authors and priests functioning as vectors).

Contemporary microbiome research is part of what, dialectically speaking, can be considered as *the negation of the negation*, which is something positive again: the unity is restored, albeit on a higher level of knowledge and awareness (for we have learned something along the way). We see microbes no longer as “other”, but as part of the web of life, as part of what we are. We see ourselves as “holobionts”

¹ This introductory chapter is based on the lecture entitled *From Autonomy to Sympoiesis: Implications of microbiome research for how we think about life, health, symbiosis and stewardship* presented by the responsible author during the *Human Microbiome Action* Final Conference in Brussels, 29 February 2024.

(Margulis and Fester 1991; Gilbert and Tauber 2016), which means that the human body is a symbiotic ensemble of interacting species, an ecosystem, containing multiple ecological niches and habitats in which a wide variety of cellular **species** collaborate.

Commenté [JD1]: ...types...

The contribution of philosophy *in science* to responsible research and sympoiesis

We see a similar dialectical process unfolding in the relationship between philosophy and life sciences research (Zwart 2022). Whereas in ancient Greece Aristotle set the standard both in philosophy and in biology (as they were both part of the same academic research practice conducted by Aristotle and his disciples), in modern times (from the scientific revolution onwards) these two epistemic cultures tended to evolve in separate directions and the initial unity became negated. During the nineteenth century, the distance between philosophy and physiology was pushed to the extreme. In the case of Nietzsche, for instance, although he was interested in science, he never actually *practiced* it. As a retired philology professor who suffered from bad health, he preferred to dwell in tourist resorts, and it is highly unlikely that he ever physically visited a laboratory or conversed with practicing scientists in person. His knowledge concerning the natural sciences came to him via selective readings, focussing on books rather than on scientific research papers, and Nietzsche himself consistently deplored this knowledge deficit (Zwart 2019).

Currently, we would argue, we witness a negation of this negation in the sense that these epistemic cultures are joining forces again. Philosophers working in teams and projects such as the HMA consortium practice *philosophy in science* (rather than philosophy of science). Epistemic cultures meet again to study complex phenomena which, besides biological and micro-biological dimensions, have philosophical, ethical, societal and cultural dimensions as well, as will be pointed out in the course of this deliverable. Although much insight has been gained during the episode of separation (via specialisation or hyper-specialisation), time has come to work together to develop a comprehensive view and ensure that microbiome research is *responsible research*. *Responsible microbiome research* means taking cultural, behavioural and socio-economic dimensions of the microbiome into account.

We could also phrase this with the help of a concept introduced in philosophy by Donna Haraway (2016), who understands living systems in terms of “sympoiesis”, so that phenomena of life are literally *produced together*, by consortia of entities. In the case of microbiome research, the *study of life* reflects

this, as the study of life likewise requires interactive and synergetic collaborations (e.g., research consortia as instances of *sympoiesis*). As will be explained more in detail below, the human microbiome itself is sometimes referred to as a collaborative “consortium”, so that HMA represents a *consortium studying a consortium*.

Knowledge, power and the self

In the next chapter we will explain that, in the context of microbiome research, the concept of responsibility and responsible innovation can be developed along three axes of reflection, building on the work of Michel Foucault (1984b). First of all, microbiome research entails new *practices of knowledge*, which includes new research methodologies and new research technologies (e.g., next generation sequencing) as well as new forms of collaboration across disciplines. Subsequently, responsibility is an important concept on the level of governance, health policy development, public health and biopolitics, thematised by Foucault as *practices of power*. Finally, we will analyse how individuals themselves can take responsibility for microbiome health in the context of what Foucault (1984b; 1984c) referred to as *practices of the self*.

Bullet points

1. Microbiome research reflects a worldview based on connectedness and embeddedness rather than separation, so that microbes are conceived as a decisive dimension of our lifeworld (the web of life) and not merely as foreign entities and pathogens.
2. The phenomena of life reflect what Donna Haraway refers to as “sympoiesis”: building living systems in a collaborative and symbiotic fashion. Organisms (including human beings) are sympoietic consortia of interdependent entities.
3. Sympoiesis is also a characteristic of research teams themselves studying the microbiome, based on interdisciplinary collaboration, where philosophy of science becomes philosophy *in science*.

Chapter 1. Taking care of our microbiome: a philosophical analysis

Responsible microbiome research

While microbiome research mostly tends to be curiosity driven (driven by the will to know), considerable implications for society may be involved, both on the collective level (where microbiome research may inform public health policies) and on the individual level (where microbiome research may inform new practices of the self). Therefore, microbiome research consortia must be aware of their societal responsibility and engage in responsible research. Emerging “practices of knowledge” such as microbiome research may give rise to new “practices of power” (microbiome governance) and new “practices of the self” (microbiome stewardship). Considerations of the societal and ethical dimensions of current microbiome research bring about the expectation that emerging tools for self-assessment and self-monitoring of the condition of our microbiome may enable us to take care of our health and well-being (as “practices of the self”, cf. HMA D7.1). The microbiome—which refers here to the combination of “trillions of microbial cells or microbiota” inhabiting the human body, along with their corresponding arrangements of genes (Ursell et al. 2012, 1204) has recently become central to the study of human health and disease (e.g., see Inkpen 2019). As between 50% to 90% of our bodily cells are microbial, the activity and composition of the microbes in our bodies have a profound impact on our overall health and well-being, not only on our metabolism and our immune system, but also on the mood and cognition (Raffaeta 2023, 3-4). These insights and approaches open up the prospect that new self-assessment technologies can become available, which may enable us to engage in knowledge-based, care-taking practices aimed at monitoring, cultivating and improving our microbial environments and relationships, diets and lifestyles, and potentially thereby also preventing a wide range of diseases both individually and beyond.

How microbiome research allows and challenges us to reconsider health policies and self-care

One way to explore these developments would be to follow a Foucauldian approach by asking the three types of questions Foucault (1984) identified, related to *knowledge*, *power* and the *self*, respectively.

As to *knowledge*, the focus will then be on new *practices of knowledge* emerging in the context of microbiome research, such as metagenomic sequencing and multi-omic integration of microbial data, connecting microbiome knowledge with insights from research areas such as nutrition science and epidemiology. In these emerging knowledge practices, we notice a shift from monocausal and linear views on human health – where a specific diagnostic tool (based on specific biomarkers for instance) suggests a specific therapeutic intervention, leading to a measurable result – towards a multi-factorial understanding of health, emphasising complexity, embeddedness, and interaction.

In terms of *practices of power*, Foucault’s concept of “biopower” (Foucault 1984a) gains importance, focussing on monitoring an influencing public health through microbiome policies, dedicated to enhancing population health by developing effective tools for behavioural change in terms of diet, lifestyle and so forth, in a more or less top-down fashion. Foucault’s concept of biopower has gained relevance during the COVID-19 pandemic, where nation states adopted rigid measures (lockdowns, quarantines, vaccination campaigns, etc.) to counteract the COVID-19 pandemic and boost preparedness, while in retrospect the question whether this “explosion of state power” was inevitable or questionable is still a matter of public dispute and scholarly debate.

Although it is unlikely that governments will resort to similar measures to boost microbiome health, the role of governments in supporting microbiome health is nonetheless a relevant topic, if only because the COVID-19 experience affected public trust in science and science-based public health policies. According to the Rathenau Institute, trust in science is quite considerable, at least in the Netherlands (Rathenau institute 2021).² There is more trust in science among Dutch citizens than in other institutions (e.g., government, courts of law, newspapers, television, trade unions, corporations). Moreover, during the corona-crisis, trust in science has increased. Still, paradoxically, public distrust in science increased as well and became more vocal in the public sphere. Many voices in contemporary societies are questioning whether scientific information is sufficiently valid, disinterested and objective, and this development is relevant for microbiome governance as well. Here, the concept of *responsible*

² <https://www.rathenau.nl/en/science-figures/impact/trust-science/public-trust-science>

microbiome research is evidently relevant. Responsible research will foster the trustworthiness of scientific information. Trust in science decreases when research, national policies and commercial interests of pharmaceutical companies become too closely entangled. This raises important questions such as: how to combine independency of research with societal relevance? And how to advise public policy and public debate on such complex issues as microbiome health?

Last but not least, we may raise the question whether microbiome research opens up opportunities for *practices of the self*, e.g. microbiome self-monitoring and microbiome stewardship. This prospect may be thought through from a “care of the self” perspective. Foucault’s concept of self-care (*souci de soi*; Foucault 1984c) may be reformulated in light of microbiome research and the prospects opened up by it.

Microbiome stewardship and care of the self as a holobiont

The expectation that recent microbiome research and self-assessment tools could enable us to take better care of our health resonates with the idea of “taking care” of our health as part of the ancient Greek ethos, as discussed by Michel Foucault in his later work. The “care of the self” entails the idea that individuals (subjects) learn about and strive to know themselves, and engage in conscious and reflective “practices of the self” in order to cultivate, improve and even refashion themselves and their modes of existence in the pursuit of an “aesthetics of existence”—along with sculpting the socio-ecological world in which their existence is embedded, giving rise to a more accomplished and comprehensive form of human *flourishing*. Here, practices of the self must build on and be informed by practices of knowledge. Rather than being egocentric or hyper-individualistic, such emerging practices of the self must become embedded in a broader culture or social ecosystem, a way of life, based on the awareness of the dependence of individual flourishing on the web of life, emphasising the connection between microbiome knowledge, ethical conduct and social and existential flourishing. This may provide us with a general framework for reflecting on the question of what it means to “take care” of ourselves as relational or symbiotic “microbial selves”, where this sense of *taking care* extends beyond the traditional notion of the individual self towards the entire microbial milieu—that is, the biosphere. The work of biologist Lynn Margulis (Margulis and Fester 1991) and others on the concept of the “holobiont” inspires us to comprehend the microbial notion of self in ecological (processual and relational) terms, and to delineate the extended scope of self-care towards taking care of our microbial selves.

Self-care and individuation

Here, we also see a connection with the concept of *individuation* developed in the work of Gilbert Simondon (2009). Whereas modern Enlightenment thinkers viewed the individual self as entering in the world fully constituted and formed, as autonomous and independent beings (e.g., the Cartesian *ego cogito* or subject of thought), Simondon views the individual as emerging from a field of “pre-individual” nature which is carried throughout the individual’s subsequent development, conceived in terms of a process ontology, or *ontogenesis*. In this view, which can only be briefly summarized here, individuals are seen as always only the momentary product of incessant and always incomplete processes of *individuation*, processes which constitute their always developing sense of individuality or psychic self.

Building on this concept of individuation, Charissa Terranova writes for instance:

“Just as a new individual emerges from the mother’s birth canal, bathed in amniotic fluids and her mother’s vaginal bacteria, which helps build her immune system for life, she emerges from a field of pre-individuation. Building on this, the individual is more properly understood as something always at work and in process, collaborating with the microbial environment inside the human body and immunologically warding off pathogenic microbes outside the human body. She is in the midst of individuation, not simply a being that is always becoming, but also, and in expanded embryological terms, always in the midst of situated biological development” (Terranova 2019, 140).

As essentially an ecological concept, Simondon’s understanding of processes of individuation allows us to include microbes into the picture of incessantly individuating and interacting *microbial selves*.

In light of this microbiomic view of ourselves (this ecologically embedded, interactive and symbiotic sense of self), the Foucauldian “care of the self” concept must be reformulated as self-care that *includes the ecological dimension of individuation*, the pre-individual realm of natural entities (e.g., microbes), as well as the psycho-social relationships which are equally significant for our becoming. This perspective invites us to reconsider not only the concept of the self, but also the concept of health, seeing it as a dynamical and multi-factorial process and as part of the process of individuation. Health cannot be understood as isolated from the internal and external environment of the individual organism and includes the entire network of ecological relationships that constitute the microbial self. This is captured by the holobiont concept which emphasizes the deep interconnectedness, interdependence, and multiplicity of organisms. It presupposes the fundamental symbiotic character of all life in the biosphere. In short, the individual organism or microbial self may be defined as a symbiotic consortium of hundreds of species: as a composite holobiont whose physiology entails co-metabolism between host and microbiome (cf.

Zwart 2022, 46). In contrast to the traditional Western view of the individual, emphasizing the autonomy, independence and self-determination of the self, microbiome research shows that we are part of a larger symbiotic web of life. We are not simply embedded and relationally dependent on a microbial milieu, but are ultimately ecosystems ourselves—composed of billions or trillions of microorganisms which make up an integral part of what we are as physical beings. In other words, while we *have* a microbiome, it must be seen as an essential part of what we *are* and how we always continue to individuate as *microbial selves*.

Commenté [JD2]: ...beings.

Simondon's notion of individuation sees individuals as part of a larger interactive web of symbiotic organisms. Microbes and the microbiome are part of our collective world, where individuals are continuously in flux. Individuals can no longer be understood solely in terms of their personal genome. Rather our individuation process involves the aggregate of genomes of trillions of microbes: the hologenome or collective genome that includes the genomes of our microbiota (Terranova 2021, 139). The microbiome works both to protect and co-activate the functioning of our physiological bodies, including our metabolism, emotional and mental well-being, and our immune system. Our holobiotic selves are changing moment by moment, with every handshake, kiss or hug (ibid.). Responsible health policies and science communication strategies must be informed by these insights. In other words, responsible health policies and science communication strategies are not only about providing factual information. They should also reflect this awareness of the connectedness of (human) life.

Rethinking self-care

If microbiome research promises to enable us to take better care of our microbial selves, the practices and techniques that may be relevant for doing so must be developed and designed in accordance with this renewed sense of health and embodiment as *fundamentally ecological and relational*. In the context that Foucault (1984c) was discussing, the ancient Greek self-care practices and techniques he studied included diet and exercise, but also meditation, self-writing, spiritual counselling, etc. In the current context in which microbiome research promises to enable new tools for microbiome self-care or self-management, allowing individuals to attend to, examine, and take care of their microbial bodies, these ancient practices and techniques may be rethought from a more contemporary perspective. This would mean that taking care of our microbial selves not only involves diet, exercise, and life-style choices, but also mental and spiritual aspects. For indeed, there is a microbiome dimension to experiences such as stress, depression or

burnout as well. Thus, microbiome awareness becomes part of the art of living. While allowing individuals to take care of their own health, informed by scientific insights, self-care involves more than the consumption of products to test or enhance our microbial condition. Rather, such tools must be combined with other practices of the self to reflect a comprehensive and relational understanding of health and individuation.

The epistemic dimension

Last but not least, there is an epistemic dimension to this as well, which also informs our “relational” (i.e. interdisciplinary) philosophy of science. The individual self, which is conceived of in terms of process of individuation by Simondon as we have seen, develops through reciprocal co-evolving relationships, not only with the pre-individual field, but also with other psychic individuals, since individuation is understood as necessarily also a collective or social individuation process. Thus, the “I” of the Cartesian *ego cogito* gives way to the “we” of a Simondonian *cogitamus* (Terranova 2019, 140), – thinking together. Thinking and reflection are no longer seen as individual but rather as collective, contextual and interactive activities. This entails a shift from the thinking ego towards thinking and reflection as a team effort. This *we* not only involves networks of human individuals, but is also embedded in the broader microbiological world, the web of life, both inside and outside the organism. There is an epistemological dimension to this, for it means that our studying and reflecting on the microbial world builds on the awareness that we ourselves are always already embedded in the web of life we aim to fathom.

Bullet points

1. Microbiome research is an emerging practice of knowledge which informs new practices of knowledge (public health policies or biopolitics) and new practices of the self (microbiome self-care).
2. Microbiome research informs our understanding of processes of individuation, seeing them as profoundly ecological and relational. This has profound implications for our understanding of human health and flourishing
3. Responsible health policies and science communication strategies are not only about providing factual information. They should reflect this awareness of the connectedness of (human) life

Chapter 2. Expert views on responsible microbiome research: interviews

Introduction

Against the backdrop of this conceptual analysis, we subsequently entered into the empirical stage of our work. How to define responsible microbiome research in practice? This part of the research consisted of three steps. First of all, we conducted a series of exploratory expert interviews, focusing on the question: what is responsible microbiome research? Subsequently, we conducted an on-line survey on public views on the microbiome. In addition, in the context of our interest of new “practices of knowledge”, we considered the implication for academic authorship, zooming in on the emerging practice of consortium authorship. In this chapter, insights provided by the interviews will be presented.

We conducted three in-depth semi-structured interviews with experts representing important knowledge perspectives: a microbiologist, a nutritionist and a bioethicist. During the interviews we asked three sets of questions: how should we see our relationship with our microbiome? How would you define microbiome health? And what constitutes responsible microbiome research? Here, we present summaries of these interviews, followed by a concise reflection, comparing the interview results with the conceptual views presented in the previous chapter.

The microbiologist

There are more cells in our gut than cells that compose the human body, and it is important for the public to be more aware of that. Human beings are ecosystems, are symbiotic beings. This first of all entails reciprocity, give and take, we give something to our microbes, and receive something in return. Notably, the microbiome maintains the homeostasis of our bodies, so that our body is in balance. In this manner, the microbiome supports us to address health challenges, ranging from cancer, obesity and diabetes up to mood problems and depression. It also means that we are not inhabited by a fixed community of microbes. Rather, the microbiome is always changing, because of mood and diet, but also due to other circumstance, and even because of weather influences.

There are companies who claim that consumers can improve the health of their microbiome via marketed products, such as dairy products enriched with certain bacterial strains, but when it comes to microbiome awareness, we must not leave it solely to companies who follow the rules of the market. Governmental policies should play a role, for instance by informing the public that the microbiome can change over time due to age or changing environments. The microbiome is also a key dimension of life events such as childbirth, as natural birth includes the passing of microbes from mother to child. This has implication for how scientists should inform the public. To care for our microbiome, rather than considering special marketed products, we should first and foremost reduce the consumption of processed food containing additives and eat more fruit and vegetables. Also, each microbiome is unique, so that special products should acknowledge the uniqueness of individual genomes. Responsible microbiome products should convey this message, that these products are part of a broader view of the relationship between food, lifestyle and health. Diversity is also important, and here one could make a comparison with monocultures in agriculture, while artificial fertilisers can perhaps be compared to antibiotics, instead of interacting with the soil microbiome in a more informed and responsible manner.

The nutritionist

Our work focusses on the question: what is a good quality diet? Dietetics looks at it from the individual level, but our work is more oriented towards public health at the population level. We are interested, for instance, in dietary diversity based on food groups. Here we notice that pregnant and breast-feeding women have different requirements than women who are not pregnant and non-lactating. We are also interested in the global diet quality project, based on the WHO question: what is a good diet? Can we measure and quantify the quality of a diet, for instance by looking at the Healthy Eating Index?

Overall, a diverse diet is better than a one-sided or unbalanced diet. It is important to broaden the perspective, however, by looking at the social environment as well, for instance the interaction between caretakers and children. This already starts at birth, as the exposure of infants during childbirth to maternal bacteria affects how well their immune systems develop later in life. Caring for your microbiome sounds like precision nutrition, but here applicability becomes important. Whether precision nutrition will be affordable for consumers will depend on access and income. People will want to take care of themselves in a way that is affordable and practically doable for them.

To be responsible means to ensure that the advice that we are giving is socially and culturally acceptable. I have worked on Pacific Islands where traditionally the food system was quite good and diverse. But then, inexpensive food products were imported from the global market, containing too much fat, sugar and sodium while not containing many micronutrients and fibres. These inexpensive food products flooded the local market and inhabitants replaced traditional healthy food with inexpensive unhealthy food. Microbiome research could enlighten us about what would have happened to the microbiome of Pacific Islanders if they would have held on to a more traditional diet compared to consuming much more convenient, tasty and processed but unhealthy food. What has happened to their microbiome? Diet-related, non-communicable diseases and obesity, high blood pressure, diabetes, etc. become more and more of a problem in these small island states. Can we make the microbiome more equitable in such a way that more research is devoted to trying to understand questions of underserved communities, and not just the priorities of Europeans and Americans? That would be my philosophical equity question, which I would write into your report.

The bioethicist

For me, an important lesson from COVID-19 public health policies is the difficulty of communicating uncertainty. How to prepare the public for scientific understanding of the microbiome being open to change? If you do not prepare the public for the possibility that your scientific insights may change, scientists may lose credibility.

As to the market for microbiome products, I think it is important to identify the kinds of self-care and self-management that people can engage in without buying any particular products. What is important is that microbiome knowledge not only leads to commercialization and the creation of products, but also to messages to the public about what they can do for their microbiome without buying anyone's products. Philosophically, people may make their own choices concerning the use of those products, provided that clear information is offered concerning harms and benefits. But there is a broader, cultural dimension to this. Although health monitoring may be beneficial in itself, it may easily result in excessive attention for our individual health as an individual project, as something we have a responsibility to engage in vigilantly. Yet there may be unintended consequences. For instance, paying excessive attention to one's health may be costly and burdensome and undermine someone's well-being in unintended ways. Responsibility means that we cannot *assume* that using these products will optimise

health, we have to consider all the ways in which consumers may be affected. It requires research into whether the use of these tools and practices affects well-being along multiple dimensions. It is not just physical health; it is also about economic considerations and psychological and emotional health. It may induce anxiety or result in social consequences. It may have systemic consequences; it may change the ways how a family eats. All these aspects, whether they are beneficial or harmful, must be considered as well.

Comments and reflections

A core message emerges from these interviews notably concerning responsible microbiome research. While fostering microbiome awareness is seen as positive and beneficial, this must be done in a comprehensive manner, holistic if you like, taking multiple dimensions and relationships into account. We must move away from a linear way of thinking, where microbiome knowledge results in marketable products which consumer may use to improve particular aspects of their microbiome health. A much more far-reaching and multi-factorial picture emerges. First of all, as the microbiologist agrees, microbiome awareness implies awareness of human individuals as symbiotic beings, in constant interaction with the microbes that inhabit us and are part of us and our environment. Also, the microbiome is in flux and constantly changing. Therefore, we should not leave microbiome awareness to companies. Microbiome awareness includes that we understand the importance of natural childbirth, for instance, and gain insight into *why* it is important to consume fruit and vegetables rather than processed food. In Foucauldian terms, microbiome research is a *practice of knowledge* which invites us to develop a more interactive, relational and embedded view on human health and well-being.

The nutritionist makes a similar argument. While this expert acknowledges the importance of efforts to define in a quantifiable manner what we mean by a healthy diet, responsible research requires a comprehensive approach, which is not limited to factual information but also takes the social context, e.g. the power dimension into account, the *practices of power* involved in this: the interaction between children and their social environment, up to the socio-economic dimension, even on a global level. Precision nutrition may not be affordable to all sections of society. The food market is permeated by practices of power, also in terms of affordability and accessibility. Here, the reference to nutritional changes on Pacific Islands is quite telling, where traditional diets were replaced by food practices based on inexpensive food products which have a detrimental impact on microbiome health. As the nutritionist

phrased it: can we make the microbiome more equitable? Rather than focussing on special products for affluent consumers, we should pay more attention to microbiome damage resulting from mass production of food items that impoverish microbiome functioning in various regions in the world.

The bioethicist agreed with this. Besides consumer consent based on information about harms and benefits, there are other *practices of the self* that allow individuals to care for their microbiome. Also, it is important to realise that information on microbiome health is complex and relational. Rather than focussing excessively on individual microbiome health (which might be a social and cultural effect of the consumption of microbiome products) we must take the broader social and cultural dimension into consideration. Microbiome health is not a purely individual project, but embedded in communities, family environments and food cultures.

As explained in the previous chapter, we see attention for microbiome health as part of an individuation process which understands human individuals as embedded and interactive beings, starting at childbirth (when not only new-borns are born, but also their microbiomes) and evolving and unfolding further, nourished by lifestyle and diets, in interaction with biological, cultural and socio-economic ecosystems.

Bullet points

1. Microbiome science communication should not focus solely on marketable products but should first and foremost foster public understanding of the microbiome as diverse, interactive, dynamic, relational, and continuously changing.
2. Responsible microbiome research should take the global social context into account, for instance by not only focussing on issues that are mostly relevant to affluent consumers in the USA and Europe, but also study the impact of the global market of unhealthy food products on local food habits in less affluent regions.
3. Deliberations about the microbiome should take the broader social and cultural dimension into account. For instance, if we assess the pros and cons of marketed microbiome products, we should not only consider the physiological consequences, but also the impact on food habits, family culture and social practices, as well as the inherent uncertainty of scientific knowledge.

Chapter 3. Online public survey

Introduction

Whereas in the previous section we discussed microbiome awareness with experts via interviews, in this section we will present a short review of our cross-national online survey on public awareness and attitudes regarding the human microbiome. A detailed account of the study, including its design, methods, analysis, and results is currently in progress and will be submitted as an academic paper in a peer-reviewed journal.

We wanted to investigate, whether the people today are inclined to recognise the role of human microbiome in their health, if they would be interested to (self-)monitor their microbiome health and actively attend to it, e.g., by adjusting one's lifestyle or using special products. Such knowledge could inform further research and contribute to healthcare policy and communication in the field.

We developed a questionnaire to investigate the following questions:

- the perceived importance of human microbiome for (1) physical health and (2) mental well-being;
- how people estimate their knowledge regarding the human microbiome;
- the major sources of information about it;
- willingness to self-monitor the health of one's microbiome;
- the preferred ways to keep one's microbiome healthy (lifestyle choices vs. consuming commercially advertised products);
- internal and external locus of control in supporting balanced microbiome (reliance on one's own feeling vs. information and techniques obtained from the doctors).
- whether awareness of human microbiome could affect how one views themselves and/or one's perception of microorganisms.

We also wanted to learn whether and how knowledge and perception of the human microbiome might differ between Eastern and Western countries with their distinct cultures and diets. Therefore, we carried out our survey in both Europe (France and Germany) and Asia (South Korea and Taiwan). The original English text of the questionnaire was translated into German, Korean and Chinese by translation agencies and into French by a native speaker from the IHMCSA Consortium.

Sampling

The survey (N=2.860) was conducted online in January 2024 in France, Germany, South Korea, and Taiwan. The recruitment and data collection were done by an external panel agency. The respondents were at least 18 years old; their age, gender and education were representative of the population of each country. The participants provided informed consent to take part in this research, and the data were anonymized. Prior to data collection, the study had been approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Erasmus School of Philosophy, Erasmus University Rotterdam, as well as pre-registered at the Open Science Foundation (OSF).

Analysis

We conducted the following analyses: descriptive statistical analyses, network modelling, and paired samples *t*-tests. Additionally, it would be possible to have the respondents' open text entries professionally translated to identify and compare patterns of responses (overall, and between different cultures/countries) by using topic modelling and sentiment analysis techniques.

Key results

The participants of our survey acknowledged the importance of human microbiome for physical health and, to a lesser degree, for mental well-being. We have found willingness to monitor the health of one's microbiome (particularly, in France and Germany), as well as to actively attend to it by adjusting one's lifestyle (in both Asian and European countries). Furthermore, after a short reflection on human microbiome the respondents reported a slightly more positive attitude towards microorganisms and the microbial realm at large. There were cross-cultural differences in the attitudes towards microbes expressed by the respondents both before and after the reflective moment. Overall, the survey showed that awareness of human microbiome could affect health behaviour, health concepts, and environmental attitudes among the general population.

Bullet points

- The participants of a large cross-national survey recognised the essential role the human microbiome plays in our health.
- The participants of the survey reported willingness to support the health of their microbiome by observing it and by adjusting one's lifestyle (e.g., diet and exercise).
- The awareness of human microbiome as an essential part of our body might contribute not only to healthier lifestyle, but also to new health concepts, to overall environmental awareness and recognising the role of microorganisms as our life partners at multiple scales.
- There were differences among the countries regarding the leading sources of information on human microbiome and the preferred ways of supporting its health, but also in the way our relationship with microbes is viewed and conceptualised in different cultures. Taking such differences into account could be relevant for national healthcare policies and communication.

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Chapter 4. Consortium authorship

Introduction

Within the HMA consortium, *consortium authorship* came up as a responsible way of publishing results of team efforts in academic journals. Whereas many HMA participants from the life sciences were familiar with the concept, for us as scholars this was relatively new. Therefore, we decided to dedicate a deliberative workshop to the pros and cons of consortium authorship resulting in an academic paper where consortium authorship (CA) is analysed in three steps: (a) via a conceptual analysis in dialogue with the scholarly literature on scientific authorship, (b) by presenting and analysing the results of a deliberative workshop on consortium authorship, and (c) by analysing how consortium authorship is currently handled in academic journals in the biomedical field. We conclude that, while technical and research ethical issues can best be addressed by combining consortium authorship with individual authorship, an *ontological* reassessment (Cronin 2001, p. 567) of authorship is required, especially in emerging practices of intense collaboration within interdisciplinary and international consortia addressing complex phenomena, such as the human microbiome (which itself is often referred to as a collaborative ‘consortium’). In this D7.3 we present a summary of design and results of our analysis. A more detailed presentation and analysis will be submitted as an academic paper to a peer-reviewed journal.

CA offers a practical solution to tenacious issues such as the question which kind of contribution qualifies for authorship and how authorship ordering is determined. CA may even be seen as an inevitable development and as a logical next step in the process of multiple authorship. There is also a positive normative dimension involved here, moreover. CA acknowledges that, in scientific collaborations, the end result is more than the sum of partial contributions attributable to individual effort. CA indicates that the research results presented in a paper could not have been achieved without intense teamwork. Moreover, consortium authorship takes us away from an individualistic view on authorship by putting more emphasis on the importance of working closely together and on mutual dependence, on the research ecosystem if you like. On the other hand, CA blurs the very concept of authorship as such. To what extent are individual contributors still responsible and accountable for a publication, for instance in cases of misconduct or fraud? Should consortium authorship be acknowledged the same way as individual authorship (by Web of Science and Google Scholar, for instance) or differently? In short, while CA offers

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benefits and opportunities compared to conventional authorship, it also raises a number of ethical questions that have not been convincingly addressed as yet (Hosseini et al 2024).

In our paper we use the HMA consortium for a case study approach, to ensure that our normative reflections are informed by practice. It is an interdisciplinary project, which means that, while some participants (especially those coming from biomedical or life sciences fields) already have significant experience with consortium authorship, for others (especially for participants coming from a humanities background) it was something both new and questionable (in the non-pejorative sense). There is an additional reason, however, for using the HMA project as a case study. The human microbiome itself, i.e. all the microbes (bacteria, fungi, viruses) living inside us, as a symbiotic community, is often referred to as a *consortium*. Thus, the HMA community is a consortium studying a consortium. As indicated in the philosophical chapter above, microbiome research takes us away from an *ego cogito* understanding of human understanding towards a more interactive, embedded and collaborative epistemology and CA may be seen as part of that. We may also refer to the phrase used by Donna Haraway, referred to above, who understands living systems in terms of “sympoiesis”, so that phenomena of life are literally *produced together*, by consortia of microbial and multi-cellular entities. In the case of microbiome research, the *study of life* reflects this, as the study of life requires interactive and synergetic collaboration (*sympoiesis*) too.

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Method

In November 2023, we organised an interactive workshop on consortium authorship, involving thirteen participants. Eight participants were researchers involved in the HMA research consortium, including the coordinator. In addition, we invited a research ethics expert, a sociology of science expert specialised in academic publishing, and a librarian. The other participants were two research assistants and a chair. We prepared eight statements for discussion, while mentimeter was used to offer an overview of initial positions for each of these statements, inviting participants to indicate whether they agreed or disagreed (on a five-point scale ranging from *strongly disagree* to *strongly agree*) with the statements presented.

Table 1. List of statements discussed during the workshop with initial scores

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1. Group authorship reduces tensions and conflicting expectations about authorship notably in large-scale projects with contributors from multiple disciplines (3.7, N= 13).
2. Group authorship acknowledges the value of academic collaboration and fosters teamwork (4.1, N=12)
3. Due to lack of persistent identifiers such as ORCID, group authorship makes it difficult to assess credibility and conflicts of interest of contributors (3.8, N=11)
4. If group authorship contributes to the citation index of a scholar in the same way as individual co-authorship, this may be seen as unfair by individual authors who made a substantial contribution (2.1, N=9).
5. In the case of PhD researchers, a group-authored paper may count as a valid part (say, a chapter) of a PhD thesis? (3.5, N=13)
6. Scientists can be members of thesis committees if they are listed as a member of a consortium involved in group authorship of one of the chapters? (3.0, N=12)
7. In the case of research misconduct, all group authors are responsible (3.2, N=12)
8. Group authorship, rather than being an option, will be enforced as an obligatory requirement, for instance when joining a research consortium (2.5, N=11).

Key results

During the workshop, CA was not seen as strategic behaviour (e.g., trying to boost the citation index of the participants involved) but rather as a consequence of promoting and acknowledging the importance of collaboration, as a key dimension of a virtuous research practice. Yet, although CA is spreading in biomedical fields, several implications still need to be thought through (Hosseini et al 2024). CA seems difficult to reconcile with academic systems of acknowledgement and reward, often focussing on authorship performance. Traditional models of authorship attribution seem increasingly at odds with how research is practiced in large-scale collaborative endeavour. Whereas other fields (e.g., high energy physics) opt for extensive lists of authors, often in alphabetical order, CA offers a viable alternative. There is a normative objective involved, namely ensuring more equitable distributions of authorship credits by putting more emphasis to the importance of collaboration while being less concerned with individual performance.

CA acknowledges that the work reported in a scholarly publication could not have been conducted without the support of the consortium as a whole. In life sciences research, CA is becoming the default rather than the exception. Yet, as Hosseini and Gordijn (2020) argue, authorship is a “two-sided coin”, with credit on the one side and responsibility on the other. While rewarding teamwork via consortium authorship seems laudable, many of the questions discussed during the workshop had to do with the responsibilities of consortium authors compared to individual authors. Here, however, a best practice is

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emerging, as was attested both during the workshop and in our analysis of journal practices, namely: *combining individual authorship with group authorship*. This would allow CA to address many of the issues listed above. While acknowledging that the work could not have been done without the consortium, some authors (listed as individual authors) made a more significant contribution and carry a larger share of the responsibility than those contributors that are solely listed as consortium members. Only if the author is listed as an individual author, preferably as the first author, can a paper be included as a chapter in a thesis. In principle, we could be satisfied with this result and present the combination of individual authorship with consortium authorship as a viable practice, offering practical solutions to most if not all of the questions that we raised.

Subsequently, we analysed twenty academic journals in the life sciences field and twenty academic journals in philosophy. To narrow down our search, we used SCImagojr.com to find papers in the highest-ranking journals. In the case of the microbiology journals involved in our search, six journals included information about CA on their website (*Nature Microbiology*, *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, *The Lancet Microbe*, *The ISME Journal*, *PLoS Pathogens*, and *NPJ Biofilms and Microbiomes*). Eight journals did not mention CA (category C), but did publish articles involving CA. Four journals neither offered information about CA as an option nor did they publish articles involving CA. In the case of the philosophy journals, we found only one journal which published a paper involving CA, but only once.

In almost all cases, the consortium is not presented as sole author, but combined with the names of individual authors. The position of the consortium in the list of authors may vary: sometimes in between individual authors, sometimes as last author. Sometimes an author is mentioned as representing the consortium, sometimes not. Subsequently, we considered where the list of authors composing the consortium is mentioned. Here, results vary. Often, the author names are mentioned in the acknowledgements, although visibility varies. Sometimes, the list of authors is mentioned elsewhere or not mentioned at all.

As indicated, whereas CA is practiced in 16 of the 20 microbiology journals, hardly any instances of CA were found in philosophy journals (the phrase “multi-centre authorship” was mentioned on a website once). This confirmed the experience during the workshop that, while most participants from microbiology and life sciences research had experience with consortium authorship, for philosophers it is a new phenomenon.

Secondly, when consortium authorship is used, it is almost always combined with individual authorship. This concurs with the results of the workshop, where the combination of CA with individual authorship (listing both individual authors and the consortium as authors) was also proposed as a best

practice. Furthermore, the name of the consortium can appear anywhere in the author list while sometimes an individual author is listed as representing the consortium as principal investigator, coordinator or contact person.

There is more to CA, however, than practical problems and solutions. For us, CA is part of a broader spectrum of changes which challenge us to rethink the concept of academic authorship as such. CA emerges when interdisciplinary consortia are established to study complex phenomena, such as the human microbiome and its relationship with health, wellbeing and cognition. We tried to capture this above by arguing that our case study (the HMA team) is *a consortium studying a consortium*. Again, we could phrase it with the help of a concept introduced in philosophy of science by Donna Haraway, who understands living systems as “sympoiesis”, so that phenomena of life are made collectively, together, by consortia of entities, and in the case of microbiome research, the *study of life* reflects this, as the interactive and synergetic study of life requires sympoiesis too. Or, as Karen Barad has argued, the traditional ontology positing a rational subject (detached from nature) versus an objectified target of research must give way to awareness of the situatedness and embeddedness of research, and CA could be seen as part of this constellation. Thus, CA becomes part of a broader transition, shifting the focus from individual performance to the functioning of knowledge ecosystems, from competitive science to team science. This is also relevant for the humanities, especially for philosophers, who often engage in interdisciplinary team work, for instance in the context of European projects, addressing the ethical, philosophical and societal aspects of life science research. Rather than detachment (philosophers seeing themselves as outsider studying the research groups involved, this should entail *working together* to come to terms with the phenomena of life (philosophy *in* science, contributing to sympoiesis, Zwart 2023).

Bullet points

1. Consortium authorship acknowledges the importance of collaboration in research, indicating that the whole result is more than the sum of contributions that are attributable to individual authors
2. In the case of consortium authorship, ambiguities concerning responsibility and contribution can best be addressed by combining consortium authorship with individual authorship
3. Consortium authorship reflects that not only life itself, but also the study of life must be considered a sympoietic endeavour (producing knowledge together)

Chapter 5. Concluding comments: relevance of our findings for the HMA consortium and for future microbiome research

This deliverable builds on our previous deliverable (D7.1) submitted a year ago (in April 2023) and focusses on ethical and governance issues in microbiome research. D7.3 reflects the progress made during the final stage of the HMA project, zooming in on the concept of responsible research. Responsible research first and foremost implies that communication of scientific findings should encompass much more than presenting the latest factual insights. Rather, microbiome research challenges the way we think about human health and individuation, offering a more connected and relational view of human existence.

First of all, microbiome research is important when it comes to reconsidering the concept of human health. In previous chapters, we explained how microbiome research deepens our understanding of human health, offering a more relational and dynamical perspective, which also takes cultural, behavioural and socio-political dimensions into account. Based on our work, we were able to contribute to the joint HMA paper on the healthy microbiome concept that was recently submitted for publication. Here we explained that notably the assessment of microbiome-based products requires a more comprehensive perspective. A large number of websites can be found on the Internet (MyBioma, MyMicrobiome, Microbiome Labs, etc.) where microbiome products are offered which allegedly allow consumers to improve their microbiome health. Often, such websites suggest that scientific microbiome knowledge translates into products which enables consumers to influence their health by adding specific components to their microbiome. As explained above, responsible research and communication must move beyond this linear causal understanding of microbiome health. Our research within the HMA project emphasises the importance of “responsible promise management” (Chadwick and Zwart 2013). Microbiome research teaches us that we are holobionts, which means that the human body is a symbiotic ensemble of interacting species, an ecosystem containing multiple ecological niches and habitats in which a wide variety of cellular species collaborate. This has ethical implications as well. Microbiome care or stewardship involves adopting a more interactive and dynamical understanding of microbiome health, as the outcome of multifactorial processes. The concept of health is difficult to define because it can have multiple meanings in various contexts. As Canguilhem (1991) argued, we must learn to think of health in

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an interactive manner, in the sense that a healthy organism can address environmental challenges and adapt to new situations. Specific tested and certified microbiome products may be helpful, but as part of a more comprehensive and functional understanding of microbial health. Such a comprehensive approach will foster the trustworthiness of microbiome research, but it evidently entails some challenges for science communication as well: how to communicate a message which emphasises the complexity and uncertainty, both of microbiome functioning and of microbiome knowledge. Again, societal interaction must include the awareness that microbiome research entails a deepened understanding of life in general and human life in particular, seeing it as deeply connected and relational.

In other words, microbiome research resonates with an emerging worldview which scholars try to capture through concepts such as symbiosis, sympoiesis and the holobiont. On the basis of the philosophical reflections developed in the *Introduction* and in *Chapter 1* of this deliverable, we contribute to two colloquia on the concept of symbiosis (within but also beyond biology), at the Catholic University of Lyon (in 2023 and 2024), organised by Béatrice de Montera, Head of SOCA Platform of the INRAE MetaGenoPolis Project. Our contributions will result in an academic paper.

One interesting outcome of the online survey we conducted is that many citizens are willing to monitor their microbiome and adjust their lifestyle to improve microbiome health. In addition, citizens are sensitive to how microbiome research fosters a relational and ecological view on human health and existence. This opens up prospects for more interactive and participatory forms of research, where the knowledge and experiences of citizens (gained in the context of practices of the self) become part of the research, in such a way that citizens not only are seen as data providers, but as active participants, contributing to the research by suggesting research questions and articulating concerns. In other words, by adopting participatory research methods, microbiome research may foster epistemic inclusion (Zwart, Barbosa and Block, 2024).

One of the pitfalls of interdisciplinary collaborations for philosophers is that their contribution is sometimes reduced to ethical and regulatory issues in the narrow sense, while knowledge practices such as microbiome research require a more comprehensive reflection, ranging from questions of worldview and human self-understanding up to the vicissitudes of academic authorship. The HMA project allowed us to adopt this more holistic approach, which we highly appreciated because, although ethical and regulatory issues, for instance concerning microbiome products are evidently important, a valid assessment requires us to look at the broader context and address cultural and socio-political dimensions as well. Building on Michel Foucault, we see microbiome care as a practice of the self which emerges in close interaction with practices of knowledge (e.g. research into microbiome health) and practices of

power (e.g., the global market of food products which are processed and inexpensive, but may have detrimental consequences for microbiome health).

Bullet points

1. Microbiome research resonates with our changing view of life, which puts more emphasis on symbiosis, connectedness and mutual dependence. This view aligns with an ethos of care, responsibility and stewardship towards our microbiome as well as towards planetary life and the environment in general in which human existence is embedded
2. Many citizens are willing to monitor their microbiome and adjust their lifestyle to improve microbiome health, which offers opportunities for participatory microbiome research and epistemic inclusion
3. Microbiome research and philosophy of science both benefit from collaborations which explore not only the physiological, but also the cultural, behavioural, socio-economic and worldview dimension of responsible microbiome research.

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